

THE IMPORTANCE OF LINGUOCULTUROLOGY IN WRITTEN TRANSLATION

Yusupov Asror

*Assistant teacher of the
department of Translation theory and practice
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

Abstract. The development of language and culture are closely related, which gave rise to the field of linguocultural science. Linguocultural studies investigate the manifestation, reflection, and strengthening of culture in language and discourse. Translation is a bilingual speech activity that plays a significant role in interlingual and intercultural communication. The translator is the central figure of international communication and mutual understanding and acts as an intermediary between multilingual and multicultural social communities. Linguocultural problems in translation arise due to a lack of cultural understanding and can lead to mistranslation or misinterpretation of the source text. To overcome these issues, a deep understanding of both the source and target cultures is necessary, including an understanding of cultural values, beliefs, and linguistic expressions.

Keywords: linguocultural science, linguocultural problems, cultural understanding, written translation, bicultural personality, non-equivalent lexicon

The main part.

The development of language and culture has been closely related to each other for a long time. This, in turn, created a new field that should be studied - linguocultural science. The study of the influence of language on culture and the influence of culture on language is leading the field today and is branching out and expanding every day. This field was created in the 90s of the 20th century, and today we can call it an independent branch of linguistics. The role of V.A. Maslova, V.N. Teliya, V.V. Vorobyev, Yu.S. Stepanova, A.D. Arutyunova, V.V. Krasnikh, who

conducted their research in this field, in the development of linguoculturology is incomparable. Because the theoretical foundations created by them are now the main resource for professors and teachers who want to work in the field of linguocultural studies and students who want to develop translation studies. The views of V.A. Maslova, V.V. Vorobyev, V.V. Krasnikh on the study of linguoculturalology are the same, and they describe it as follows: "Linguoculturology is a science that arose at the intersection of linguistics and cultural studies, it studies the manifestation of national culture reflected in language "It is a science that studies the manifestation, reflection, and strengthening of culture in language and discourse" [5.12p].

Translation as a bilingual speech activity is the basis of interlingual and intercultural communication, which carries out the process of getting to know a foreign culture: At the same time, translation is considered not only a process of interlingual, but also intercultural communication, in which a secondary translation text is created on the basis of a targeted translation analysis of the source text, replacing the original in a new linguistic and cultural environment.

The translator performs the social function of an intermediary between multilingual and multicultural social communities and is the central figure of international communication and mutual understanding, therefore the methodology of teaching translation should set itself the task of developing various competencies that allow the future translator, both in the field of philology and in the field of linguistics and intercultural communication, to become "a person at the turn of cultures" or "bicultural personality".

Therefore, the translator, as a representative of one culture, is not only specific to his own language but also forms the characteristics of another conceptual system, as well as intercultural competence, which is useful in translation studies, and ensures that individuals go beyond their culture and without losing their own culture. It is a mediator that informs about other cultures. Since the specific characteristics of native speakers' culture are reflected in different linguistic and cultural images of the world and cognitive structures are expressed in inconsistencies, translators, as

people who know different languages, should be able to correctly convey cultural units and distinguish cultural differences between languages in the process of written translation.

The translation is an essential tool for communication between cultures, but it is not without its challenges. One of the most significant difficulties in translation is dealing with linguocultural problems. These issues arise when the cultural context of the source language is not fully understood or appreciated by the translator. In this article, we will explore the linguocultural problems of translation, their causes, and their potential impact.

Culture is an important aspect of language. It shapes the way people think, communicate, and behave. When a translator translates a text, they are not just converting words from one language to another. They are also transferring cultural meanings and ideas. Therefore, a lack of cultural understanding can lead to mistranslation or misinterpretation of the source text.

One of the major causes of linguocultural problems in translation is the assumption of universalism. This assumption is the belief that all human experiences and values are the same, regardless of cultural differences. It can lead to a lack of attention to the cultural context in translation. For example, the phrase "time is money" is a commonly used expression in English, but it may not make sense in some cultures where time is not valued in the same way.

Another cause of linguocultural problems in translation is ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism is the belief that one's own culture is superior to others. This attitude can lead to the imposition of one culture's values and beliefs on another. In translation, this can lead to the loss of cultural features and meaning in the source text.

According to V.P.Neroznak, when we talk about the concept of national culture, when we translate it into another language, there is no equivalent word for any concept in that language: "non-equivalent lexicon, or as it is usually called "untranslatable words", the words are a real lexicon, on the basis of which it is

necessary to compile a list of fundamental national-cultural concepts” (Neroznak, 1998).

Cultural differences can also cause ambiguity in translation. For example, in some cultures, the use of indirect language is preferred, while in others, direct language is favored. This can lead to confusion and misunderstanding when translating from one language to another. Similarly, some cultures have different ways of expressing politeness and respect, which can be lost in translation if not properly understood by the translator.

The impact of linguocultural problems in translation can be significant. Mistranslations can lead to misunderstanding, confusion, and even offense. In some cases, mistranslations can have legal or financial implications. For example, a mistranslation of a contract can result in legal disputes and financial losses.

To overcome linguocultural problems in translation, it is essential to have a deep understanding of both the source and target cultures. This includes an understanding of the cultural values, beliefs, and behaviors that underpin the languages being translated. It is also important to work with a translator who has expertise in the relevant cultural context.

Translators can also employ a variety of strategies to avoid linguocultural problems. One approach is to use localization. Localization involves adapting a product or service to the language and culture of the target market. This approach can help ensure that the translated text is culturally appropriate and meaningful to the target audience.

Another approach is to use a team of translators with different cultural backgrounds. This can help to ensure that the translation considers the cultural features of both the source and target languages.

Translators can also use cultural mediation strategies, such as cultural adaptation, cultural substitution, and cultural explanation. Cultural adaptation involves modifying the source text to make it more appropriate for the target culture. Cultural substitution involves replacing culturally specific terms with more familiar

ones in the target culture. The cultural explanation consists in providing additional context to help the target audience better understand the cultural references in the source text.

According to Micaela Muñoz-Calvo, “We have to accept that the old world has gone. Cultural/ethnic/regional identity and globalization interface and there are political, economic, social and linguistic implications. Translation plays an undeniable role in the shaping of cultures, of national identities, and it is the vehicle that may make compatible the strengthening of our group identity and consequent knowledge of our own culture with the sharing and learning of other cultures; cultures and their texts becoming accessible and available to international audiences in their own language” [3, 5p].

Strategies for Navigating Linguocultural Differences in Translation

Navigating linguocultural differences is a key challenge for translators, and there is a range of strategies that they can use to help them do so effectively. Some of these strategies include:

Conducting Research: One of the most important strategies for navigating linguocultural differences is to conduct research on the culture and language of the target audience. This can involve studying cultural norms, idiomatic expressions, and other linguistic features that are unique to the target culture. By doing so, translators can gain a deeper understanding of the linguistic and cultural features that are present in the target language and can use this knowledge to guide their translation process.

Adapting Language Use: In some cases, it may be necessary for translators to adapt their language use in order to effectively communicate with the target audience. This can involve altering the tone or style of the text to better align with the cultural norms and values of the target audience. For example, a text that is humorous in the source language may need to be translated in a more serious tone in order to resonate with a target audience that does not value humor in the same way.

Using Contextual Cues: Another strategy that translators can use to navigate linguocultural differences is to rely on contextual cues in the original text. This can include paying close attention to the tone and style of the text, as well as to any contextual information that may be present. By doing so, translators can gain a better understanding of the intended meaning of the text and can use this information to guide their translation process.

Working with Bicultural Translators: In some cases, it may be beneficial to work with translators who are bicultural, meaning that they have a deep understanding of both the source and target cultures. These translators can provide valuable insights into the cultural features that may be present in the original text and can help to ensure that the translated text accurately reflects the intended meaning of the source text.

Conclusion

In conclusion, linguocultural problems are a significant challenge for translators who are seeking to accurately convey the meaning of a text across languages. These problems can arise in a range of linguistic features, including grammar, vocabulary, and syntax, as well as in broader cultural concepts such as politeness and social hierarchies. To effectively navigate these challenges, translators must be able to conduct research, adapt their language use, use contextual cues, and work with bicultural translators.

REFERENCES

1. Asror, Y. (2023). LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK VA FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLAR TARJIMASIDA LEKSIKOGRAFIYANING QO‘LLANISH O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI. IQRO JURNALI, 1(2), 311-316.
2. Asror, Y. (2020). Methods of translation of socio-political texts (with the examples of English language). Наука и образование сегодня, (4 (51)), 35-38.
3. Gómez, M. D. C. B., & Muñoz-Calvo, M. (Eds.). (2010). Translation and cultural identity: Selected essays on translation and cross-cultural communication. Cambridge Scholars Publishing. 5p
4. Neroznak, V. P. (1998). From concept to word: to the problem of philological conceptualism In Problems of Philology and methods of teaching foreign languages.
5. Красных В.В. Этнопсихоллингвистика и лингвокультурология: Курс лекций. – М.ИТДГК. “Гнозис”, 2002. - С.12;
6. Kudratovich, D. N. (2023). СИНХРОН ТАРЖИМА ҚИЛИШДА ҚЎЛЛАНИЛАДИГАН АЙРИМ УСУЛЛАР ТАСНИФИ. IQRO JURNALI, 1(2), 322-330.
7. Sherzodovich, A. S., & Jamshedovich, B. F. THE MAIN FEATURES OF THE TRANSLATION OF LITERARY TEXT. Sciencepublish. org, 16.
8. Abdirasulov, B. (2021). CLASSIFICATION OF LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL TRANSFORMATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal, (1).
9. Қўлдошов, Ў. Ў. (2022). БАДИИЙ ТАРЖИМАНИНГ ЛИНГВОМАДАНИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(1), 670-678.
10. Yusupov, O. Y. (2020). ETYMOLOGICAL AND PRO-ETYMOLOGICAL DOUBLETS IN ENGLISH. Theoretical & Applied Science, (2), 417-420.

11. Yusupov, O., Yoqubjonova, S., & Abduvokhidova, S. (2022). THE BENEFITS OF HAVING OVERALL 7.0 FROM IELTS IN DIFFERENT AREAS OF LIFE. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(5), 213-215.

12. Юсупов, О. (2022). Хорижий тилларни ўқитишда таржиманинг аҳамияти. *Анализ актуальных проблем, инноваций, традиций, решений и художественной литературы в преподавании иностранных языков*, 1(01), 9-11.

13. Yusupov, O. (2016). TESTING AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL OF AN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM. In *Непрерывное образование в современном мире: история, проблемы, перспективы* (pp. 233-236).

14. Tukhtasinov, I., & Otabek, Y. (2022). Teaching a Foreign Language According to Age Groups. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice*, 22(2), 238-246.

15. FJ, B. (2023). The polysystem theory of subtitling. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(2), 468-471.